

<https://ejournal.uit-lirboyo.ac.id/index.php/noumerico>
<https://doi.org/10.33367/jtme.v2i2.5352>

Development of Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Four Variables ($w, x, y, \text{ and } z$), Three Variables ($x, y, \text{ and } z$), and Two Variables ($x \text{ and } y$)

Kifilideen Osanyinpeju^{1*}

¹Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta Ogun State

amkifilideenosanyinpeju@gmail.com

*Correspondence

Abstract

Article Information:

Received April 28,
2024

Revised August 29,
2024

Accepted August 29,
2024

Keyword:

Simultaneous
Equations, Four
Variables, Three
Variables, Two
Variables, Matrix
Elimination Method

The Gaussian elimination method of solving four variables of simultaneous equations involves eliminating some elements of the simultaneous equations in triangular form to zero to determine the values of the variables of the simultaneous equations. This approach does not involve a matrix in generating the values of variables of the simultaneous equations. There is a need to develop a matrix model for solving four variables of simultaneous equations. The pattern of the developed model can be extended by solving three variables and two variables of simultaneous equations. This study develops Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of four variables $w, x, y \text{ and } z$, three variables $x, y \text{ and } z$ and two variables $x \text{ and } y$. The elimination method was gradually used to reduce the number of variables of a given simultaneous equation in matrix form. In contrast, in the process, Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was generated to solve the values of the variables of the simultaneous equations. The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was implemented in solving four variables $w, x, y \text{ and } z$, three variables $x, y \text{ and } z$ and two variables $x \text{ and } y$ simultaneous equations. Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model has been fully utilised, attractive, accurate, and easy to understand.

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a branch of science that studies the pattern of arrangement and formulation of events, systems, objects and structures (Luo et al., 2021). Understanding the pattern of progression of events, systems, objects, and structures has led to many discoveries of models, formulas and equations (Kaiser et al., 2018; Yadav, 2019; Wedin, 2020). The beauty of mathematics is that it is dynamic and progressing but not static (Osanyinpeju, 2019). What mathematics requires is commitment, time, effort and much interaction with figures, shapes or numbers in different ways for new models, formulas, and equations to be generated and established (Çelik et al., 2020; Osanyinpeju, 2020a; Osanyinpeju, 2021).

The understanding and assimilation of new models, formulas and equations can be built into oneself by continuously interacting and implementing the models, formulas and equations (Osanyinpeju, 2022). As it is known, you know more about and have a

better understanding of something when you continue to interact with that thing in different ways (Osanyinpeju, 2020b) more so as you have less interaction with something you know less of it (Osanyinpeju, 2020c).

Simultaneous equations are two or more equations with the same unknown variables in which the values of the variable satisfy all the equations (Grcar, 2011b). The known methods of solving simultaneous equations are the elimination method, substitution method, graphical method, crammer's rule, inverse matrix method and Gaussian elimination method (Ugboduma, 2013; Woollard, 2015). Gaussian elimination method of solving four variables of simultaneous equations involves eliminating some elements of the simultaneous equation in triangular form to zero to determine the values of the variables of the simultaneous equation (Grcar, 2011a). This approach does not involve a matrix in generating the values of variables of the simultaneous equations (Luo et al., 2021). There is a need to develop a matrix model for solving four variables of simultaneous equations, and the pattern of the developed model can be extended to solving three variables and two variables of simultaneous equations. This study develops Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y . Implementing Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model generates the values of the variables of the simultaneous equations.

Literature Review

1. Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Two Variables

The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of two variables x and y is presented as follows:

The simultaneous equation of two variables x and y is given as:

$$ax + by = k \quad \text{row 1} \quad (1)$$

$$cx + dy = m \quad \text{row 2} \quad (2)$$

To establish Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate y , then we have

So, we first eliminate y in (1) and (2):

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix} x + \begin{vmatrix} b & b \\ d & d \end{vmatrix} y = \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & d \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix} x = \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & d \end{vmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array}$$

To establish Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find y , we first eliminate x , then we have:

So, we first eliminate x in (1) and (2):

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & a \\ c & c \end{vmatrix} x + \begin{vmatrix} b & a \\ d & c \end{vmatrix} y = \begin{vmatrix} k & a \\ m & c \end{vmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} b & a \\ d & c \end{vmatrix} y = \begin{vmatrix} k & a \\ m & c \end{vmatrix}$$

In general, the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of two variables x and y is given as:

To find x :

$$\begin{matrix} C_x & C_y & C_s & C_y \\ \left| \begin{matrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{matrix} \right| x = & \left| \begin{matrix} k & b \\ m & d \end{matrix} \right| & \begin{matrix} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{matrix} \end{matrix} \quad (3)$$

To find y :

$$\begin{matrix} C_y & C_x & C_s & C_y \\ \left| \begin{matrix} b & a \\ d & c \end{matrix} \right| y = & \left| \begin{matrix} k & a \\ m & c \end{matrix} \right| & \begin{matrix} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{matrix} \end{matrix} \quad (4)$$

The coefficients of the variable x , C_x in equations (1) and (2) are a and c , while the coefficients of the variable y , C_y in equations (1) and (2) are b and d . The coefficients of the system s , C_s in equations (1) and (2) are k and m . For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Models (3) and (4), the number of columns is four (2^2); two columns from the left-hand side and two columns from the right side of the model. Also, for Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Models (3) and (4), the number of rows is four (2^2): two rows from the left-hand side and two rows from the right side of the model.

For all the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Models (3) and (4) to find the variables x and y , says variable x ; the first column at the left (1^{st} column of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model) is the coefficients of the variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x . In contrast, the first column at the right (3^{rd} column of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model) is the coefficient of the system's constant, C_s . The even columns (2^{nd} and 4^{th} column of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model) are the coefficients of the variable y (eliminated variable), C_y . 1^{st} , 2^{nd} , 3^{rd} and 4^{th} columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variables x and y ; says variable x ; contains the coefficients, C_x , C_y , C_s and C_y respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y , C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, C_x-1 column, C_y-2 columns and C_s-1 column. Row 1 and row 2 of the models (3) and (4) are the coefficients of Rows 1 and Row 2 in (1) and (2), respectively, in line with the identities of x , y and s .

2. Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Two Variables

The Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of three variables x , y and z is presented below:

The simultaneous equation of three variables x , y and z is given as:

$$ax + by + cz = k \quad \text{row 1} \quad (5)$$

$$dx + ey + fz = m \quad \text{row 2} \quad (6)$$

$$gx + hy + jz = n \quad \text{row 3} \quad (7)$$

To generate Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate any of y or z , and then eliminate the one that was not eliminated in the first elimination.

To establish Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate y , then

we have:

So, to generate Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate y in (5) and (6), and (6) and (7).

From (5) and (6), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} b & b \\ e & e \end{vmatrix}y + \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} \\ \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array} \quad (8)$$

From (6) and (7), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{vmatrix} d & e \\ g & h \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} e & e \\ h & h \end{vmatrix}y + \begin{vmatrix} f & e \\ j & h \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} m & e \\ n & h \end{vmatrix} \\ \begin{vmatrix} d & e \\ g & h \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} f & e \\ j & h \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} m & e \\ n & h \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array} \quad (9)$$

From (8) and (9), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{vmatrix} d & e \\ g & h \end{vmatrix}x + \begin{vmatrix} f & e \\ j & h \end{vmatrix}z &= \begin{vmatrix} m & e \\ n & h \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \end{array} \quad (11)$$

To find x , we further eliminate z in (10) and (11), so we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{matrix} C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_z & C_y \\ \left| \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix} \right| & x = & \left| \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix} \right| \end{matrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

If we eliminate x in (10) and (11) in order to find z , so we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{matrix} C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_x & C_y \\ \left| \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix} \right| & z = & \left| \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix} \right| \end{matrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Following the pattern of arrangement in the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model established in (12) and (13), the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to solve for y if x is eliminated first and z is then eliminated, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{matrix} C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_z & C_x \\ \left| \begin{vmatrix} b & a \\ e & d \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} c & a \\ f & d \end{vmatrix} \right| & y = & \left| \begin{vmatrix} k & a \\ m & d \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} c & a \\ f & d \end{vmatrix} \right| \end{matrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

In general, the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of three variables x , y and z is given as:

To find x , if y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{matrix} C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_z & C_y \\ \left| \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ d & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} c & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix} \right| & x = & \left| \begin{vmatrix} k & b \\ m & e \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ f & e \end{vmatrix} \right| \end{matrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (15), where y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second, we have 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7rd and 8th columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $C_x, C_y, C_z, C_y, C_s, C_y, C_z$ and C_y respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is C_x – 1 column, C_y – 4 columns C_z – 2 columns and C_s – 1 column. Row 1, Row 2, Row 3 and Row 4 of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model model (15) are the coefficients of rows 1, row 2, row 2 and Row 3 in (5) to (7), respectively, in line with the identities of x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if z is first eliminated and y is eliminated second

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cc|cc} C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} a & c & b & c \\ d & f & e & f \end{array} \right| & x = & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} k & c & b & c \\ m & f & e & f \end{array} \right| & \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{array} \quad (16)$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (16), where z is first eliminated, and y is eliminated second, we have 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7rd and 8th columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $C_x, C_z, C_y, C_z, C_s, C_z, C_y$ and C_z respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is C_x – 1 column, C_z – 4 columns C_y – 2 columns and C_s – 1 column. Row 1, Row 2, Row 3 and Row 4 of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model model (16) are the coefficients of rows 1, row 2, row 2 and Row 3 in (5) to (7), respectively, in line with the identities of x, y, z and s .

To find y , if z is first eliminated and x is eliminated second

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cc|cc} C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_x & C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} b & c & a & b \\ e & f & d & e \end{array} \right| & y = & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} k & c & a & c \\ m & f & d & f \end{array} \right| & \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} \end{array} \quad (17)$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable y in (17), where z is first eliminated, and x is eliminated second, we have 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7rd and 8th columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $C_y, C_z, C_x, C_z, C_s, C_z, C_x$ and C_z respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y (the variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable x

To find z , if y is first eliminated and x is eliminated second

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cc|cc}
 C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_x & C_y \\
 \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} c & b & a & b \\ f & e & d & e \\ f & e & d & e \\ j & h & g & h \end{array} \right| z = \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} k & b & a & b \\ m & e & d & e \\ m & e & d & e \\ n & h & g & h \end{array} \right| & \begin{array}{l} \text{row 1} \rightarrow \text{Row 1} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 2} \\ \text{row 2} \rightarrow \text{Row 3} \\ \text{row 3} \rightarrow \text{Row 4} \end{array} & (20)
 \end{array}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (20), where y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second, we have 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7rd and 8th columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $C_z, C_y, C_x, C_y, C_s, C_y, C_x$ and C_y respectively. So, the coefficients of variable z (the variable we are looking for), C_z appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is $C_z - 1$ column, $C_y - 4$ columns $C_x - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. Row 1, Row 2, Row 3 and Row 4 of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model model (20) are the coefficients of rows 1, row 2, row 2 and Row 3 in (5) to (7), respectively in line with the identities of x, y, z and s .

For all the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix models (15) to (20) to find the variables x, y and z ; the first column at the left (1st column of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model) is the coefficients of the variable we are looking for while the first column at the right (5th column of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model) is the coefficients of the constant of the system, C_s . The coefficients of the first eliminated variable are the even columns (2nd 4th 6th and 8th columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model). The remaining columns (3rd and 7th columns of Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix model) are the coefficients of the second eliminated variable.

3. Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Four Variables w, x, y and z

The Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to proffer solutions to simultaneous equations of four variables $w, x, nd z$ is illustrated below:

The simultaneous equation of four variables $w, x, nd z$ is given as:

$$aw + bx + cy + dz = r \quad \text{row 1} \quad (21)$$

$$ew + fx + gy + hz = s \quad \text{row 2} \quad (22)$$

$$iw + jx + ky + lz = t \quad \text{row 3} \quad (23)$$

$$mw + nx + py + qz = v \quad \text{row 4} \quad (24)$$

To generate Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate any of w, y or z ; say w ; then eliminate any of y or z ; say y ; then eliminate z .

To establish Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate w , then we have:

So, to generate Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find x , we first eliminate w in (21) and (22), (22) and (23), and (23) and (24).

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_z & C_x \\
 \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\|
 \end{array}
 \quad y = \quad (32)$$

In general, the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of four variables w, x, y and z is given as:

To find w , if x is first eliminated, y is eliminated second, and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_w & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_y & C_x \\
 \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\|
 \end{array}
 \quad w = \quad (33)$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (33), where x is first eliminated and y is eliminated second, and z is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th, and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model, which contains the coefficients $(C_w, C_x, C_y, C_x), (C_z, C_x, C_y, C_x), (C_s, C_x, C_y, C_x), (C_z, C_x, C_y, C_x)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of the variable w The variable we are looking for, C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of the variable x (first eliminated variable) C_x appear in eight columns, the coefficients of the variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of the variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns, and the coefficients of the system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_x - 8$ columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_z - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (33) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find w , if x is first eliminated, z is eliminated second, and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_w & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_z & C_x \\
 \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ k \\ j \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\|
 \end{array}
 \quad w = \quad (34)$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (34), where x is first eliminated and z is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have ($1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}$), ($5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}$), ($9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}$), ($13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and 16^{th}) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_w, C_x, C_z, C_x) , (C_y, C_x, C_z, C_x) , (C_s, C_x, C_z, C_x) , (C_y, C_x, C_z, C_x) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable w (the variable we are looking for), C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of variable x (first eliminated variable) C_x appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_x - 8$ columns, $C_z - 4$ columns, $C_y - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (34) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find w , if y is first eliminated, z is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_w & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & c \\ s & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & g \\ t & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & g \\ t & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & k \\ v & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} w = \dots \tag{35}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (35), where y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have ($1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}$), ($5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}$), ($9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}$), ($13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and 16^{th}) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_w, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_x, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_s, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_x, C_y, C_z, C_y) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable w (the variable we are looking for), C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable x (third eliminated variable), C_x appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_y - 8$ columns, $C_z - 4$ columns, $C_x - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (35) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find w , if y is first eliminated, x is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_w & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_x & C_y \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & c \\ s & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & g \\ t & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & g \\ t & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & k \\ v & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} w = \tag{36}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (36), where y is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_w, C_y, C_x, C_y), (C_z, C_y, C_x, C_y), (C_s, C_y, C_x, C_y), (C_z, C_y, C_x, C_y)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable w (the variable we are looking for), C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_y - 8$ columns, $C_x - 4$ columns, $C_z - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (36) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find w , if z is first eliminated, x is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_w & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & d \\ e & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & d \\ f & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & d \\ g & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & d \\ f & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & d \\ s & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & d \\ f & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & d \\ g & h \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & d \\ f & h \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & h \\ i & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & h \\ k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & h \\ t & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & h \\ k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & h \\ i & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & h \\ k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & h \\ t & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & h \\ k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & h \\ j & l \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & l \\ m & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & l \\ n & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & l \\ p & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & l \\ n & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & l \\ v & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & l \\ n & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & l \\ p & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & l \\ n & q \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} w = \tag{37}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (37), where z is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_w, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_y, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_s, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_y, C_z, C_x, C_z)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable w (the variable we are looking for), C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$

columns, $C_x - 4$ columns, $C_y - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (37) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find w , if z is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} a & d & c & d \\ e & h & g & h \\ e & h & g & h \\ i & l & k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} b & d & c & d \\ f & h & g & h \\ f & h & g & h \\ j & l & k & l \end{array} \right| & C_s & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} e & h & g & h \\ i & l & k & l \\ i & l & k & l \\ m & q & p & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} f & h & g & h \\ j & l & k & l \\ j & l & k & l \\ n & q & p & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} r & d & c & d \\ s & h & g & h \\ s & h & g & h \\ t & l & k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} s & h & g & h \\ t & l & k & l \\ s & h & g & h \\ v & q & p & q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} b & d & c & d \\ f & h & g & h \\ f & h & g & h \\ j & l & k & l \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} e & h & g & h \\ i & l & k & l \\ i & l & k & l \\ n & q & p & q \end{array} \right| \end{pmatrix} w = \dots \tag{38}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable w in (38), where z is first eliminated and y is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_w, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_x, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_s, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_x, C_z, C_y, C_z) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable w (the variable we are looking for), C_w appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable x (third eliminated variable), C_x appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$ columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_x - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (38) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

To find x , if y is first eliminated, z is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_x & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_w & C_y & C_z & C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} b & c & d & c \\ f & g & h & g \\ f & g & h & g \\ j & k & l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} a & c & d & c \\ e & g & h & g \\ e & g & h & g \\ i & k & l & k \end{array} \right| & C_s & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_w & C_y & C_z & C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} f & g & h & g \\ j & k & l & k \\ j & k & l & k \\ n & p & q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} e & g & h & g \\ i & k & l & k \\ i & k & l & k \\ m & p & q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} r & c & d & c \\ s & g & h & g \\ s & g & h & g \\ t & k & l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} s & g & h & g \\ t & k & l & k \\ s & g & h & g \\ v & p & q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} a & c & d & c \\ e & g & h & g \\ e & g & h & g \\ i & k & l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} b & c & d & c \\ f & g & h & g \\ f & g & h & g \\ n & p & q & p \end{array} \right| \end{pmatrix} x = \dots \tag{39}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (39), where y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_x, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_w, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_s, C_y, C_z, C_y) , (C_w, C_y, C_z, C_y) respectively. So, the

coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable w (third eliminated variable), C_w appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_y - 8$ columns, $C_z - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (39) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if y is first eliminated, w is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_x & C_y & C_w & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_w & C_y & C_s & C_y & C_w & C_y & C_z & C_y & C_w & C_y \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & c \\ f & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & c \\ h & g \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & c \\ e & g \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c} s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & g \\ j & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c} m \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & g \\ l & k \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & g \\ i & k \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & k \\ n & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right| & & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right| & & & & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & k \\ q & p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & k \\ m & p \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} x = \tag{40}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (40), where y is first eliminated and w is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_x, C_y, C_w, C_y), (C_z, C_y, C_w, C_y), (C_s, C_y, C_w, C_y), (C_z, C_y, C_w, C_y)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable w (second eliminated variable), C_w appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_y - 8$ columns, $C_w - 4$ columns, $C_z - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (40) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if z is first eliminated, w is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_x & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_w & C_z \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} x = \dots \tag{41}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (41), where z is first eliminated and w is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_x, C_z, C_w, C_z) , (C_y, C_z, C_w, C_z) , (C_s, C_z, C_w, C_z) , (C_y, C_z, C_w, C_z) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable w (second eliminated variable), C_w appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$ columns, $C_w - 4$ columns, $C_y - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (41) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if z is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_y & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} x = \dots \tag{42}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (42), where z is first eliminated and y is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_x, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_w, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_s, C_z, C_y, C_z) , (C_w, C_z, C_y, C_z) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable w (second eliminated variable), C_w appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$

columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (42) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if w is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{matrix} C_x & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_s & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_y & C_w \\ \left| \begin{matrix} b & a \\ f & e \\ j & i \\ n & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} c & a \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} d & a \\ h & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} e & a \\ i & e \\ m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & x = & \left| \begin{matrix} r & a \\ s & e \\ t & i \\ v & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} c & a \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} d & a \\ h & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} e & a \\ i & e \\ m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} f & e \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} h & e \\ i & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} j & i \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} n & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} o & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} p & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right|
 \end{matrix} \tag{43}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (43), where w is first eliminated and y is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have ($1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}$), ($5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}$), ($9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}$), ($13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and 16^{th}) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_x, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_s, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_y, C_w)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable w (first eliminated variable) C_w appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_w - 8$ columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_z - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (43) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find x , if w is first eliminated, z is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{matrix} C_x & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_s & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_z & C_w \\ \left| \begin{matrix} b & a \\ f & e \\ j & i \\ n & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} d & a \\ h & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} c & a \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} e & a \\ i & e \\ m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & x = & \left| \begin{matrix} r & a \\ s & e \\ t & i \\ v & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} d & a \\ h & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} c & a \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} e & a \\ i & e \\ m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} f & e \\ g & e \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} h & e \\ i & e \\ l & i \\ q & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} j & i \\ k & i \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} m & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} n & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} o & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right| & \left| \begin{matrix} p & e \\ p & m \end{matrix} \right|
 \end{matrix} \tag{44}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (43), where w is first eliminated and z is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have ($1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}$), ($5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}$), ($9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}$), ($13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and 16^{th}) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients,

$(C_x, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_s, C_w, C_y, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_y, C_w)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable x (the variable we are looking for), C_x appear in one column, the coefficients of variable w (first eliminated variable) C_w appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_x - 1$ column, $C_w - 8$ columns, $C_z - 4$ columns, $C_y - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (44) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

To find y , if z is first eliminated, w is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_y & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_w & C_z \\
 \left\| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right\| & \left\| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right\|
 \end{array}
 y = \dots \tag{45}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable x in (45), where z is first eliminated and w is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have $(1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}), (5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}), (9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}), (13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and $16^{th})$ columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_y, C_z, C_w, C_z), (C_x, C_z, C_w, C_z), (C_s, C_z, C_w, C_z), (C_x, C_z, C_w, C_z)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y The variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of the variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of the variable w (second eliminated variable), C_w appear in four columns, the coefficients of the variable x (third eliminated variable), C_x appear in two columns, and the coefficients of the system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_y - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$ columns, $C_w - 4$ columns, $C_x - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (45) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find y , if z is first eliminated, x is eliminated second, and w is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_y & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_s & C_z & C_x & C_z & C_w & C_z & C_x & C_z \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| \\
 \end{array} y = \dots \tag{46}$$

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable y in (45), where z is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_y, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_w, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_s, C_z, C_x, C_z), (C_w, C_z, C_x, C_z)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y (the variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of variable z (first eliminated variable) C_z appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable w (third eliminated variable), C_w appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_y - 1$ column, $C_z - 8$ columns, $C_x - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (46) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find y , if w is first eliminated, x is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_y & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_s & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_z & C_w & C_x & C_w \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| \\
 \end{array} y = \dots \tag{47}$$

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable y in (47), where w is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_y, C_w, C_x, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_x, C_w), (C_s, C_w, C_x, C_w), (C_z, C_w, C_x, C_w)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y (the variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of variable w (first eliminated variable) C_w appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_y - 1$ column, $C_w - 8$

$(C_y, C_x, C_z, C_x), (C_w, C_x, C_z, C_x), (C_s, C_x, C_z, C_x), (C_w, C_x, C_z, C_x)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y (the variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of variable x (first eliminated variable) C_x appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable z (second eliminated variable), C_z appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable w (third eliminated variable), C_w appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_y - 1$ column, $C_x - 8$ columns, $C_z - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (49) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find y , if x is first eliminated, w is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc}
 C_y & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_z & C_x & C_w & C_x \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & b \\ g & f \\ g & f \\ k & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & b \\ e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & b \\ h & f \\ h & f \\ l & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & b \\ e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & y = & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & b \\ s & f \\ s & f \\ t & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & b \\ e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & b \\ h & f \\ h & f \\ l & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} a & b \\ e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & f \\ k & j \\ k & j \\ k & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & f \\ h & f \\ l & j \\ l & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & f \\ s & f \\ t & j \\ t & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \\ i & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & f \\ h & f \\ l & j \\ l & j \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} e & f \\ e & f \\ i & j \\ i & j \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & j \\ k & j \\ k & j \\ p & n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & j \\ i & j \\ i & j \\ m & n \end{array} \right| & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & j \\ l & j \\ l & j \\ q & n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & j \\ i & j \\ i & j \\ m & n \end{array} \right| & & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & j \\ t & j \\ t & j \\ v & n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & j \\ i & j \\ i & j \\ m & n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & j \\ l & j \\ l & j \\ q & n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} i & j \\ i & j \\ i & j \\ m & n \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} \tag{50}$$

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable y in (50), where x is first eliminated and w is eliminated second and z is eliminated third, we have $(1^{st}, 2^{nd}, 3^{rd}, 4^{th}), (5^{th}, 6^{th}, 7^{th}, 8^{th}), (9^{th}, 10^{th}, 11^{th}, 12^{th}), (13^{th}, 14^{th}, 15^{th}$ and $16^{th})$ columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, $(C_y, C_x, C_w, C_x), (C_z, C_x, C_w, C_x), (C_s, C_x, C_w, C_x), (C_z, C_x, C_w, C_x)$ respectively. So, the coefficients of variable y (the variable we are looking for), C_y appear in one column, the coefficients of variable x (first eliminated variable) C_x appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable w (second eliminated variable), C_w appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable z (third eliminated variable), C_z appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s, C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_y - 1$ column, $C_x - 8$ columns, $C_w - 4$ columns, $C_z - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (50) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

To find z , if w is first eliminated, x is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_z & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_s & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_x & C_w \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & a \\ h & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & a \\ s & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & e \\ l & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & i \\ q & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & i \\ v & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & i \\ v & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} z = \dots \tag{51}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (51), where w is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_z, C_w, C_x, C_w) , (C_y, C_w, C_x, C_w) , (C_s, C_w, C_x, C_w) , (C_y, C_w, C_x, C_w) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable z (the variable we are looking for), C_z appear in one column, the coefficients of variable w (first eliminated variable) C_w appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable y (third eliminated variable), C_y appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_z - 1$ column, $C_w - 8$ columns, $C_x - 4$ columns, $C_y - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model (51) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find z , if w is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_z & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_s & C_w & C_y & C_w & C_x & C_w & C_y & C_w \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} d & a \\ h & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} r & a \\ s & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} b & a \\ f & e \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} c & a \\ g & e \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} h & e \\ l & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} s & e \\ t & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} f & e \\ j & i \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} g & e \\ k & i \end{array} \right| \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c|c} l & i \\ q & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & i \\ v & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} t & i \\ v & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} j & i \\ n & m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c|c} k & i \\ p & m \end{array} \right|
 \end{array} z = \dots \tag{52}$$

For Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (52), where w is first eliminated and y is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen’s Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_z, C_w, C_y, C_w) , (C_x, C_w, C_y, C_w) , (C_s, C_w, C_y, C_w) , (C_x, C_w, C_y, C_w) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable z (the variable we are looking for), C_z appear in one column, the coefficients of variable w (first eliminated variable) C_w appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable x (third eliminated variable), C_x appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_z - 1$ column, $C_w - 8$ columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_x - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row

3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (52) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find z , if x is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_z & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_y & C_x \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| \\
 \end{array} z = \dots \tag{53}$$

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (53), where x is first eliminated and y is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_z, C_x, C_y, C_x) , (C_w, C_x, C_y, C_x) , (C_s, C_x, C_y, C_x) , (C_w, C_x, C_y, C_x) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable z (the variable we are looking for), C_z appear in one column, the coefficients of variable x (first eliminated variable) C_x appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable y (second eliminated variable), C_y appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable w (third eliminated variable), C_w appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_z - 1$ column, $C_x - 8$ columns, $C_y - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (53) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

OR

To find z , if x is first eliminated, w is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cccc|cccc|cccc|cccc}
 C_z & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_s & C_x & C_w & C_x & C_y & C_x & C_w & C_x \\
 \left| \begin{array}{c} d \\ h \\ h \\ l \\ h \\ l \\ l \\ q \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} r \\ s \\ s \\ t \\ s \\ t \\ t \\ v \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} c \\ g \\ g \\ k \\ g \\ k \\ k \\ p \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} a \\ e \\ e \\ i \\ e \\ i \\ i \\ m \end{array} \right| & \left| \begin{array}{c} b \\ f \\ f \\ j \\ f \\ j \\ j \\ n \end{array} \right| \\
 \end{array} z = \dots \tag{54}$$

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (54), where x is first eliminated and w is eliminated second and y is eliminated third, we have (1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th), (5th, 6th, 7th, 8th), (9th, 10th, 11th, 12th), (13th, 14th, 15th and 16th) columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_z, C_x, C_w, C_x) , (C_y, C_x, C_w, C_x) , (C_s, C_x, C_w, C_x) , (C_y, C_x, C_w, C_x) respectively. So, the

For Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to find the variable z in (56), where y is first eliminated and x is eliminated second and w is eliminated third, we have (1^{st} , 2^{nd} , 3^{rd} , 4^{th}), (5^{th} , 6^{th} , 7^{th} , 8^{th}), (9^{th} , 10^{th} , 11^{th} , 12^{th}), (13^{th} , 14^{th} , 15^{th} and 16^{th}) columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model which contains the coefficients, (C_z, C_y, C_x, C_y) , (C_w, C_y, C_x, C_y) , (C_s, C_y, C_x, C_y) , (C_w, C_y, C_x, C_y) respectively. So, the coefficients of variable z (the variable we are looking for), C_z appear in one column, the coefficients of variable y (first eliminated variable) C_y appear in eight columns, the coefficients of variable x (second eliminated variable), C_x appear in four columns, the coefficients of variable w (third eliminated variable), C_w appear in two columns and the coefficients of system s , C_s appear in one column. That is, $C_w - 1$ column, $C_y - 8$ columns, $C_x - 4$ columns, $C_w - 2$ columns and $C_s - 1$ column. The Row 1, Row 2, Row 3, Row 4, Row 5, Row 6, Row 7 and Row 8 of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model (56) are the coefficients of the rows 1 row 2, row 2 rows 3, row 2, row 3, row 3 and row 4 in (21) to (24) respectively in line with the identities of w, x, y, z and s .

For all the models (33) to (56) to find the variables w, x, y and z ; the first column at the left (1^{st} column of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model) is the coefficients of the variable we are looking for while the first column at the right (9^{th} column of the model) is the coefficients of the constant of the system, C_s . The even columns (2^{nd} , 4^{th} , 6^{th} , 8^{th} , 10^{th} , 12^{th} , 14^{th} , and 16^{th} columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix model) are the coefficients of the first eliminated variable, the odd columns 3^{rd} , 7^{th} , 11^{th} and 15^{th} columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix model) are the coefficients of the second eliminated variable and the remaining odd columns 5^{th} and 13^{th} columns of the Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix model are the coefficients of the third eliminated variable

METHOD

The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y was established using elimination and matrix ideology. Elimination method was gradually used to reduce the numbers of variables of a given simultaneous equation in matrix form where in the process Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was generated to solve the values of the variables of the simultaneous equations. Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model of solving simultaneous equations of four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y is a model of elements of simultaneous equations into series of 2×2 matrix where within each model there exist a variable to be determined. This is one type of writing where it functions as a theory surgery. Explaining in detail the theory that applies to all n applied to some of the simpler n so that it is easier to understand by people who are still in the "weighty" stage of advanced mathematics

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was implemented in solving four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y simultaneous equations.

1. Utilization of Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Two Variables x and y

(1) Find variables x and y using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model:

$$3x + 5y = 11 \quad (57)$$

$$2x - 3y = 1 \quad (58)$$

Solution

Using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve for x , assuming y is first eliminated, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cc|c} C_x & C_y & C_s & C_y \\ \hline 3 & 5 & 11 & 5 \\ 2 & -3 & 1 & -3 \end{array} x = \begin{array}{cc|c} C_s & C_y \\ \hline 11 & 5 \\ 1 & -3 \end{array} \quad (59)$$

$$-19x = -38 \quad (60)$$

$$x = \frac{-38}{-19} = 2 \quad (61)$$

Using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve for y , assuming x is first eliminated, we have:

$$\begin{array}{cc|c} C_y & C_x & C_s & C_x \\ \hline 5 & 3 & 11 & 3 \\ -3 & 2 & 1 & 2 \end{array} y = \begin{array}{cc|c} C_s & C_x \\ \hline 11 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 \end{array} \quad (62)$$

$$19x = 19 \quad (63)$$

$$x = \frac{19}{19} = 1 \quad (64)$$

$$x = 2, \text{ and } y = 1 \quad (65)$$

2. Implementation of Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Three Variables x, y and z

(1) Solve the simultaneous equation using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model

$$4x - y + 2z = 5 \quad (66)$$

$$2x + y - 3z = -1 \quad (67)$$

$$x - 2y + 6z = 7 \quad (68)$$

Solution

Using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve for x , assuming y is first eliminated then z is eliminated second, we have:

To find x , if y is first eliminated and z is eliminated second, we have:

$$\begin{array}{c} C_x \quad C_y \quad C_z \quad C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 4 & -1 & 2 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & -3 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 & -3 & 1 \\ 1 & -2 & 6 & -2 \end{array} \right| x = \begin{array}{c} C_s \quad C_y \quad C_z \quad C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 5 & -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & -3 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & -3 & 1 \\ 7 & -2 & 6 & -2 \end{array} \right| \end{array} \quad (69)$$

$$\left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 6 & -1 & 4 & -1 \\ -5 & 0 & -5 & 0 \end{array} \right| x = \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 4 & -1 & -5 & 0 \end{array} \right| \quad (70)$$

$$-5z = -5 \quad (71)$$

$$x = \frac{-5}{-5} = 1 \quad (72)$$

To find z, if y is first eliminated and x is eliminated second, we have:

$$\begin{array}{c} C_z \quad C_y \quad C_x \quad C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 2 & -1 & 4 & -1 \\ -3 & 1 & 2 & 1 \\ -3 & 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 6 & -2 & 1 & -2 \end{array} \right| z = \begin{array}{c} C_s \quad C_y \quad C_x \quad C_y \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 5 & -1 & 4 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 2 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 7 & -2 & 1 & -2 \end{array} \right| \end{array} \quad (73)$$

$$\left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} -1 & 6 & 4 & 6 \\ 0 & -5 & -5 & -5 \end{array} \right| z = \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 4 & 6 & -5 & -5 \end{array} \right| \quad (74)$$

$$5z = 10 \quad (75)$$

$$z = \frac{10}{5} = 2 \quad (76)$$

To find y, if z is first eliminated and x is eliminated second, we have:

$$\begin{array}{c} C_y \quad C_z \quad C_x \quad C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} -1 & 2 & 4 & 2 \\ 1 & -3 & 2 & -3 \\ 1 & -3 & 2 & -3 \\ -2 & 6 & 1 & 6 \end{array} \right| y = \begin{array}{c} C_s \quad C_z \quad C_x \quad C_z \\ \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 5 & 2 & 4 & 2 \\ -1 & -3 & 2 & -3 \\ -1 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 7 & 6 & 2 & 6 \end{array} \right| \end{array} \quad (77)$$

$$\left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} 1 & -16 & -13 & -16 \\ 0 & 15 & 15 & 15 \end{array} \right| y = \left| \begin{array}{cc|cc} -13 & -16 & 15 & 15 \end{array} \right| \quad (78)$$

$$15y = 45 \quad (79)$$

$$y = \frac{45}{15} = 3 \quad (80)$$

$$x = 1, y = 3 \text{ and } z = 2 \quad (81)$$

3. Utilization of Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Four Variables w, x, y and z

(1) Solve the simultaneous equation using Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model

$$3w - 5x + y - 2z = 0 \quad (82)$$

$$7w - 2x + 4y - 3z = 18 \quad (83)$$

$$w - x + y + 3z = 10 \quad (84)$$

$$-5w + 2x - 3y + z = -15 \quad (85)$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} -5 & -29 \\ -3 & 5 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} -5 & -29 \\ -24 & 5 \end{vmatrix} y = \begin{vmatrix} -54 & -29 \\ -52 & 5 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} -5 & -29 \\ -24 & 5 \end{vmatrix} \quad (97)$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} -112 & -721 \\ 1 & 8 \end{vmatrix} y = \begin{vmatrix} -1778 & -721 \\ 19 & 8 \end{vmatrix} \quad (98)$$

$$-175y = -525 \quad (99)$$

$$y = \frac{-525}{-175} = 3 \quad (100)$$

To find w , assuming z is first eliminated, y is eliminated second and x is eliminated third, we have:

$$\begin{vmatrix} C_w & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ 3 & -2 & 1 & -2 \\ 7 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 7 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 7 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -5 & 1 & -3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ -5 & -2 & 1 & -2 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & -3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} w = \begin{vmatrix} C_s & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ 0 & -2 & 1 & -2 \\ 18 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 18 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 10 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 18 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ 10 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 10 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -15 & 1 & -3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} C_x & C_z & C_y & C_z \\ -5 & -2 & 1 & -2 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -2 & -3 & 4 & -3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ -1 & 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & -3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \quad (101)$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} 5 & 5 \\ 24 & 15 \\ 24 & 15 \\ 16 & 10 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} 11 & 5 \\ -9 & 15 \\ -9 & 15 \\ -7 & 10 \end{vmatrix} w = \begin{vmatrix} 36 & 5 \\ 84 & 15 \\ 84 & 15 \\ 55 & 10 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} 11 & 5 \\ -9 & 15 \\ -9 & 15 \\ -7 & 10 \end{vmatrix} \quad (102)$$

$$\begin{vmatrix} -45 & 210 \\ 0 & 15 \end{vmatrix} w = \begin{vmatrix} 120 & 210 \\ 15 & 15 \end{vmatrix} \quad (103)$$

$$-675w = -1350 \quad (104)$$

$$w = \frac{-1350}{-675} = 2 \quad (105)$$

$$w = 2, x = 1, y = 3 \text{ and } z = 2 \quad (106)$$

CONCLUSION

This study develops Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to solve simultaneous equations of four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y . The elimination method was gradually used to reduce the number of variables of a given simultaneous equation in matrix form, whereas, in the process, Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was generated to solve the variables of the simultaneous equation. The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model was implemented to solve four variables w, x, y and z , three variables x, y and z and two variables x and y simultaneous equations. The Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model has been fully utilized and found effective, interesting, accurate, easy to understand and utilize

REFERENCES

- Çelik, H. C., Siirt University Faculty of Education, & Özdemir, F. (2020). Mathematical Thinking as a Predictor of Critical Thinking Dispositions of Pre-service Mathematics Teachers. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(4), 81–98. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2020.268.6>
- Grcar, J. F. (2011a). How ordinary elimination became Gaussian elimination. *Historia Mathematica*, 38(2), 163–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hm.2010.06.003>
- Grcar, J. F. (2011b). *Mathematicians of Gaussian Elimination*. 58(6).
- Kaiser, G., Forgasz, H., Graven, M., Kuzniak, A., Simmt, E., & Xu, B. (Eds.). (2018). *Invited Lectures from the 13th International Congress on Mathematical Education*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72170-5>
- Luo, H., Wu, S., & Xie, N. (2021). Three methods for solving systems of linear equations: Comparing the advantages and disadvantages. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2012(1), 012061. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2012/1/012061>
- Oliveri G. (1997). Mathematics. A Science of Patterns? *Synthese* 112: 379 – 402.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2019). Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11) and Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) Tables. 1st International Conference on Engineering and Environmental Sciences (ICEES) Theme: Advancing Technology and Environment Burdens (Challenges and Sustainable Solution 5th - 7 th November 2019 pg 957 – 968.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2020a). Development of Kifilideen (Power of Base 11), Antikifilideen (Antipower of Base 11) and Other Tables. Eliva Press SRL Publisher, MD-2060, bd. Cuza-Voda, ¼, of. 21 Chisinau, Republica Moldova, Europe 136 pgs.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2020b). Development of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem Using Matrix Approach. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology* 7 (7): 117- 135.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2020c). Utilization of Kifilideen Trinomial based on Matrix Approach in Computation of the Power of Base of Tri-Digits Number. *International Conference on Electrical Engineering Applications (ICEEA 2020)*, Department of Electrical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. September 23-25, 2020 Pp 192 – 199.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2021). Inauguration of Negative Power of – of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem using Standardized and Matrix Methods 5 (1): 17 – 23.
- Osanyinpeju K.L. (2022). Derivation of Formulas of the Components of Kifilideen Trinomial Expansion of Positive Power of N with Other Developments 18 (1): 1 – 21.
- Ugboduma, O. (2013). Students' Preference of Method of Solving Simultaneous Equations. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 11(2), 129–136. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v11i2.8>

- Wedin, H. (2020). *Mathematical Induction. U.U.D.M. Project Report* (Department of Mathematics).
- Woollard, L. (2015). Planning for progression- the debate around the use of the elimination method in the teaching of simultaneous equations. *The STeP Journal*, 2(2).
- Yadav, S. (2019). *ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY*. 6(4).